

Report on developments that lead to improvements in ESM throughput

Deliverable ID	D10.1
Work Package Reference	10 – Model developments for realistic and efficient ER-ESMs
Issue	1.1
Due Date of Deliverable	30/09/2024
Submission Date	24/09/2024
Dissemination Level	Public
Lead Partner	BSC
Contributors	AWI, BSC, MPG MPI-M
Grant Agreement No	101081383
Call ID	HORIZON-CL5-2022-D1-02-02

**Funded by
the European Union**

ETH Zürich's contribution to EERIE is funded by the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI) under contract #22.00366.

All UK Partners in EERIE are funded by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee (grant numbers 10057890, 10049639, 10040510, 10040984).

Prepared by AWI, BSC, MPG MPI-M	Reviewed by ECT, EPO	Approved by ECT, EPO
---	--------------------------------	--------------------------------

Issue	Date	Description	Author
1.0	09/08/2024	First issue of the deliverable	AWI, BSC, MPG MPI-M
1.1	24/09/2024	Additions and revisions accepted; layout finalised	ECT, EPO

Index

Index.....	3
Executive Summary	4
1 Profiling and optimizations	6
1.1 ICON.....	6
1.2 IFS-FESOM.....	6
1.3 IFS-NEMO.....	8
1.3.1 Strong scaling tests	8
1.3.2 CPU profiling analysis.....	13
1.3.3 I/O profiling analysis	19
1.3.4 IFS checks and diagnostics impact.....	25
1.3.5 LUMI environment variables	26
1.3.6 NEMO mixed precision plan.....	28
1.3.7 NEMO GPU transition plan	29
2 Impact and exploitation	33
3 General issues and workarounds.....	34
4 Conclusions and future work.....	34
5 References	35

Executive Summary

This document offers an overview of the efforts to achieve computationally efficient eddy-resolving configurations to run the EERIE simulations of different climate models: ICON, IFS-FESOM and IFS-NEMO. The common main goal for all the models is to achieve a good throughput, necessary to perform expensive and long simulations to save computational resources.

Different machines are used for each model. ICON has been deployed on JSC and DKRZ machines, such as Levante, using a heterogeneous setup, consisting of CPUs for the ocean and GPUs for the atmosphere. So far, since this setup is not optimised yet, the throughput is similar to running fully on CPU-only, but using much less nodes.

Another machine from JSC, in this case Juwels, has been used to deploy the IFS-FESOM model. Several actions have been carried out to overcome initial issues due to the particularities of Juwels, not present in other machines. Also, different improvements have been implemented, including an optimised coupling, as well as a better MultIO setup, such as tuning the cores and threads pinning. Some barriers were also introduced in the FESOM model to improve the stability and address some bugs causing race conditions. In addition, the remapping weight between the ocean and atmospheric models has been refined to have better efficiency and conservation. In general terms, all these improvements lead to approximately a 55% increase in the throughput.

Finally, IFS-NEMO has been deployed on LUMI and more recently to the newest available Marenostrum 5. A thorough scalability analysis with and without I/O is performed on both LUMI and Marenostrum 5. Then a detailed CPU profiling analysis of IFS-NEMO is performed, with a special emphasis on NEMO since it is revealed to have more computational bottlenecks than IFS. Among all the bottlenecks, we can highlight that the OpenMP parallelization is not efficient, there are workload imbalances and the MPI communication for some specific regions is not efficient. In addition, the profiling allowed us to identify a list of user functions with different properties that make them suitable to start the GPU porting. On the other hand, since I/O becomes a critical issue for high-resolution simulations, there is a comprehensive profiling analysis of the MultIO server.

Some small improvements have also been explored for IFS-NEMO regarding two aspects. Firstly, IFS has several scientific checks that have been tuned to avoid their expensive cost. Secondly, some LUMI environment variables that were used for stability purposes, have been thoroughly tested to determine which ones are strictly necessary to minimise their impact in the throughput.

Last but not least, there are two large and crucial optimizations ongoing, which are the implementation of a NEMO mixed precision version, and also a NEMO GPU transition. Since these are two long-term tasks, this deliverable only reports the plans, and results will be reported in the next deliverable.

This document is organised as follows: Section 1 describes the achieved and ongoing computational performance developments of the ICON, IFS-FESOM and IFS-NEMO climate

models; Section 2 analyses how the current and future work is aligned with the associated project objectives; Section 3 lists some of the main issues faced and the applied workarounds; Section 4 summarises the work done and briefly describes the next tasks; and Section 5 contains the bibliography used.

**Funded by
the European Union**

ETH Zürich's contribution to EERIE is funded by the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI) under contract #22.00366.

All UK Partners in EERIE are funded by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee (grant numbers 10057890, 10049639, 10040510, 10040984).

1 Profiling and optimizations

1.1 ICON

We upgraded the horizontal resolution of coupled ICON from a 10km-10km (ocean-atmosphere) to a 5km-10km, but instead decreased the ocean vertical resolution from 128 levels to 72 levels. Here, the 5km ocean resolution is desired in order to be globally eddy resolving, but this placed a large burden on computational resources and throughput, and hence we reduced the number of vertical levels in ICON-O to balance the cost to some extent. Some changes to radiation time step, number of atmospheric substeps and time slices of high-frequency outputs helped to increase throughput.

We have worked on getting the coupled ICON model to run on a heterogeneous setup on Jülich SuperComputing machines (JSC). This heterogeneous setup employs GPUs for the atmospheric component and CPUs for the oceanic component. Since it is not yet optimised, the throughput is similar to running fully on CPU-only (450 nodes) on Levante machines in DKRZ, but on noticeably much less nodes (32 GPUs and 57 CPUs).

Currently, EERIE production runs are performed on Levante and the performance with about 9 months per day is below our expectations. Reasons are that even with a higher priority granted, single chunks of integrations spend too much waiting time in the queue due to the relatively high demand of nodes (see above) and the fact that the model still integrates quite unstable. Regarding the high demand of nodes, a solution with a heterogeneous setup also on Levante is envisaged. As of today, we expect a delay with our production runs.

1.2 IFS-FESOM

The EERIE Phase 1 simulations for IFS-FESOM are performed on the Juwels cluster. To be as efficient as possible in running these ambitious simulations, the primary focus of this phase has been on configuring the model on Juwels and achieving decent throughput, a task that has not been done before. Initially, we encountered many hurdles in successfully performing simulations with different nodal configurations. The Juwels cluster configuration is unique, and each node is less capable compared to other machines such as Levante or Lumi, particularly regarding the number of cores and available memory. Therefore, it faces some unique difficulties and limitations not encountered on other machines. After resolving some of the initial challenges, we managed to simulate with a few nodal configurations, achieving a throughput of approximately 6.5 to 7 months per day using 320 computing nodes and an additional 40 I/O nodes with MultIO. However, stability of the simulation remained an issue.

Further efforts have focused on enhancing both throughput and stability of the simulations. One significant improvement involved optimising the coupling between the atmosphere and ocean

models, which exhibited greater imbalance on the Jewels cluster compared to other systems. To address this, we transitioned from a point-to-point (p2p) information transfer approach to a point-to-all (p2a) method, which significantly reduced the imbalance percentage from around 12% to 2% associated with the coupling process.

Additionally, we optimised the MultiIO-related I/O nodes, determining that 20 I/O nodes are optimal for handling the I/O tasks in the Tco1279-NG5 configuration. This optimization ensured efficient data management and minimised bottlenecks. We also fine-tuned the cores and threads pinning to enhance computational efficiency.

To improve stability and address a bug related to race conditions, we introduced additional barriers in the FESOM model. These measures helped eliminate potential node congestion and ensured smoother execution. We experimented with different UCX settings (DC or RC) on Jewels to assess their impact on model performance and stability.

Moreover, we refined the remapping weights between the ocean and atmospheric grids, aiming for greater efficiency and conservation. These efforts collectively contributed to a more robust and performance simulation environment on the Jewels cluster with a lesser number of failures during the simulation. To summarise the result of our effort so far, in Figure 1, we show the improvement in performance (in terms of simulation day per day) that we could achieve compared to the performance we got initially. It shows an estimated increase of around 100 simulation days per day when we implement the above-mentioned changes in the Jewels. However, we have not the attribution of how much individual changes exactly contribute to the increase in performance.

Figure 1: The performance of IFS-FESOM in tco1279-NG5 configuration in Jewels cluster (in terms Simulation days per day) initially (in blue) and at present (in orange) after the optimisation efforts

1.3 IFS-NEMO

The EERIE Phase 1 simulations for IFS-NEMO are performed using IFS CY48R1 and NEMO 4.0.7 SI3, resolutions Tco1279 for IFS and eORCA12 for NEMO, and simulating HighResMIP-coupled (1950-2100).

1.3.1 Strong scaling tests

The strong scalability tests for the Tco1279-eORCA12 resolution of the IFS-NEMO model were conducted on the CPU partition of the LUMI supercomputer (LUMI-C), splitting the study into a first scalability test without I/O and a second study with the default I/O setup enabled. A preliminary strong scaling test was also conducted in the pre-operational Marenostrum 5 supercomputer.

Table 1 contains the hardware specifications of both machines:

	LUMI-C	Marenostrum 5
CPU model	2x AMD EPYC 7763, with 64 cores (128 threads with hyperthreading) running max. at 2.45 GHz	2x Intel Xeon Platinum 8480+ with 112 cores (224 threads with hyperthreading) running max. at 3.80 GHz
NUMA nodes	4 (16 cores per NUMA node)	2 (56 cores per NUMA node)
Memory per node	256 GiB	256 GiB
L1d Cache	4 MiB (128 instances)	5.3 MiB (112 instances)
L2 Cache	64 MiB (128 instances)	224 MiB (112 instances)
L3 Cache	512 MiB (16 instances)	210 MiB (2 instances)
Filesystem	Parallel Lustre filesystem No local storage at the node	GPFS Parallel filesystem 960GB NVMe local storage
Network	Cray Slingshot-11 with 50 GB/s bidirectional	ConnectX-7 NDR200 InfiniBand (shared by two nodes, 100Gb/s bandwidth per node)

Table 1: LUMI-C and Marenostrum 5 specifications

The methodology used in this study was to run, with different node counts, the same configuration while gathering the throughput of the model for a 5-day forecast length. We discard the initialization and finalisation time in the throughput computation as they are negligible in long simulations of the model.

1.3.1.1 Strong scalability test without I/O on LUMI-C

The scalability test without I/O aimed to find the best configuration of the model on the LUMI-C supercomputer in terms of MPI tasks per node and threads per task. We decided to study two configurations using all the 128 threads available in one LUMI-C node, using 8 threads per task with 16 MPI tasks per node and 16 threads per task with 8 MPI tasks per node. The LUMI CPU partition can extend up to 256 threads per node using hyper-threading technology, but we discarded this after some small tests.

Figure 2: Throughput (left) and speed-up (right) comparison between 8 and 16 OpenMP threads executions

Figure 2 (left) depicts the throughput averaged across two executions. The x-axis represents the computing nodes used, not the total nodes allocated for the experiment. Eight additional nodes were allocated for I/O (4 for IFS and 4 for NEMO), which remained idle throughout the execution. These nodes, though not impacting model performance, are excluded. The performance comparison shows better results for the configuration using 8 threads than using 16 threads per MPI task. This distinction is notably substantial; at 64 nodes, the difference hovers around 10%, while at 288 nodes, it increases to approximately 25%.

As presented in Figure 2 (right), with 8 threads per task, the scalability is quite good compared with the ideal case, while with 16 threads scaling starts deteriorating above 230 nodes as shown in the dark-blue curve.

1.3.1.2 Strong scalability test with I/O on LUMI-C

Using the best node configuration of the strong scaling test without I/O (8 threads per task and 16 MPI tasks per node) we continue the strong scalability analysis enabling the I/O of the model, aiming to see the real throughput of the model and the overhead of the I/O. To save resources, only a subset of the executions of the I/O test were executed.

The selected setup for this I/O study includes 16 nodes for I/O servers, eight I/O nodes for both NEMO and IFS respectively. Figure 3 contrasts the SDPD values with and without output enabled, showing the overhead in the black series of the plot. The I/O overhead scales up to 20 % with 156 computing nodes.

IFS-NEMO I/O throughput comparison

Average of two executions in LUMI-C

Figure 3: Throughput comparison between I/O enabled and disabled, plotted in the left y-axis. The I/O overhead is plotted using the right y-axis

1.3.1.3 Strong scalability test without I/O on Marenstrum 5

We repeated the scalability test for Marenstrum 5 using the eight and four-thread configurations using the Intel compiler and the Intel MPI library. We also executed some simulations using 16 threads per MPI task but these results were discarded since we observed that the throughput was worse than the other configurations. Figure 4 shows the comparison between both configurations in terms of throughput and scalability. The four-thread executions with 700, 750, and 800 nodes crashed due to a virtual memory error.

IFS-NEMO Strong scaling throughput

10 days forecast, 1 execution

IFS-NEMO Strong scaling throughput

10 days forecast, 1 execution

Figure 4: Throughput(top) and speed-up(bottom) comparison between 8 and 4 OpenMP threads executions

Complementary to this study, we also executed the model with the Intel compiler and the OpenMPI library, Figure 5 shows the comparison between the two libraries for the 8-thread per task configuration.

Intel and OpenMPI IFS-NEMO throughput

10 day forecast, 1 execution

Intel and OpenMPI IFS-NEMO throughput

10 day forecast, 1 execution

Figure 5: Intel MPI and Open MPI performance comparison

As noted before, at the time of this execution Marenostrom 5 is in a pre-operational phase, meaning that these results have to be considered preliminary.

1.3.1.4 Strong scalability test with I/O (reduced output) on Marenostrom 5

One of the I/O configurations we tested was the development resolution with reduced output to support the 1950 coupled spinup. We dedicated one computing node to each IFS and NEMO I/O servers because it is enough to process the data without blocking the model. This study helps to see the overhead on the client side derived from the I/O compared to the scaling without I/O.

Figure 6 shows the throughput comparison between the simulations with reduced I/O and without I/O using the 8-thread configuration. We can see that the I/O version is consistently 5% slower than the version without I/O, except for the 300-node case, which is an outlier due to hardware variability.

Figure 6: IFS-NEMO Scalability comparison without I/O and with reduced plans

1.3.2 CPU profiling analysis

We conducted the profiling analysis of the IFS-NEMO4.0 model using Extrae [4] and Paraver [5], from the BSC profiling toolset. Extrae intercepts different parallel programming model calls and generates trace files that can be displayed and analysed with Paraver. Figure 7 shows an overview of the workflow of these two tools.

Figure 7: Overview of Extrae and Paraver (BSC Tools)

This analysis was carried out mainly on LUMI and Marenostrum4 because of the incompatibility of the OpenMP tracing on LUMI with the BSC tools. We chose a 1-hour forecast execution for efficiency, using 80 nodes, 8 threads per task, and 16 tasks per node for the LUMI execution and 82 nodes with the same thread and task setup. The goal of this profiling was to address MPI or OpenMP bottlenecks that are slowing the model.

The trace was split into three sub-traces: one for IFS, another for the coupling phase, and one for NEMO. The schematic in Figure 8 shows an overview of the different phases of execution. The coupling phase and the initialization and finalisation of the whole model were not analysed.

Figure 8: IFS-NEMO4.0 computation phases per timestep

1.3.2.1 General profiling

For the first approach to the model performance, we use the POP [6] efficiency metrics. These metrics are relative percentages of an ideal execution and are hierarchically computed. The definitions of the metrics are:

- Serialisation efficiency: It measures how much the code is serialised such as waiting due to dependency chains, imbalances that are compensated, etc.
- Transfer efficiency: It measures the time devoted to transferring data.
- Communication efficiency: It measures the loss of efficiency that is not caused by the global load imbalance, this is, due to serialisation and transfer.
- Load balance: It measures how globally balanced work is between all processes/threads.
- Parallel efficiency: It measures how efficient the parallelization is by calculating which percentage of time is computation and which percentage of time the application is in the runtime (e.g. executing MPI code).

Table 2 reports the POP metrics for the two programming paradigms of the model (multithreading with OpenMP and distributed memory with MPI) for IFS and NEMO respectively.

Metric	IFS	NEMO
≡ MPI Parallel efficiency	79.27	75.27
≡≡ MPI Load balance	94.68	84.29
≡≡≡ MPI Communication efficiency	83.72	89.30
≡≡≡≡ Serialization efficiency	100.00	100.00
≡≡≡≡ Transfer efficiency	83.72	89.30
≡ OpenMP Parallel efficiency	89.45	69.72
≡≡ OpenMP Load Balance	74.89	62.26
≡≡≡ OpenMP Communication efficiency	119.44	111.99

Table 2: Hybrid POP metrics comparison between IFS and NEMO

In comparing both models, Table 2 shows a better performance for IFS in the OpenMP and the MPI efficiency. The most limiting factor in the NEMO is the OpenMP load balancing, meaning that it is either a problem with the workload balancing or a huge serial region not parallelized with OpenMP. Because of this poor performance of NEMO, we will focus the profiling analysis on the NEMO side of the IFS-NEMO model in the next section.

1.3.2.2 NEMO profiling

This section will analyse the subroutines involved in the NEMO timestep, completing the efficiency metrics presented in Table 2. The goal is to find explanations for the low OpenMP parallel efficiency metric and find bottlenecks that are slowing down the performance. We will use the BSC tools to conduct this study.

Figure 9 shows the multithreading performance overview, plotting the average number of threads used in useful computation (neither MPI communication nor OpenMP synchronisation), across all the tasks in the execution of one NEMO timestep. We observe large time areas where the average is one thread, meaning a lack of OpenMP parallelization or a highly serialised code (i.e. barriers).

Figure 9: Average amount of useful threads per task for a NEMO time-step

Figure 10 shows the global parallel efficiency (instantaneous parallelism) combining the OpenMP and MPI parallel metrics. Several subroutines have very low parallel efficiency, highlighting `sbc_wave`, `ice_dyn_rdgfrt` and `dynspg_ts` as the most time-consuming subroutines and the worst efficiency metric.

Figure 10: Percentage of resources used over time (blue function line) for one NEMO time-step

After the general overview of the NEMO timestep performance, now we are going to focus on each subroutine detected in Figures 9 and 10. The goal is to understand the low parallel efficiency detected.

The first region in the timestep with poor parallel efficiency is the `sbc_wave`, which accounts for 15% of the whole NEMO timestep. Figure 11 (left) plots the useful compute duration (colour gradient) for some processes in the `sbc_wave` subroutine. Here we can observe how the useful duration varies per process (y-axis), i.e., the amount of work computed by each thread. From this plot, we can observe a high load imbalance in this region both at MPI and OpenMP levels. To determine the source of the imbalance, Figure 11 (right) shows the correlation between useful duration and the number of instructions in this region. On the y-axis, there are the different processes and on the x-axis the computation duration. The colour indicates (with a gradient scale, green low, blue high) the number of instructions executed. We observe how the colour gradient correlates with the x-axis position, confirming that the load imbalance comes from a higher load in the number of instructions executed. With this information, we can discard a variation in the number of instructions per cycle (IPC) or a change in the clock frequency as the cause of the load imbalance.

Figure 11: Useful duration zoom to some processes of the `sbc_wave` subroutine (left) and number of instructions (colour) per process (y-axis) for useful duration (x-axis) (right)

Besides the imbalance in the number of instructions, we also noticed that the communication, which accounts for the 20% of the total time spent in this subroutine, keeps the non-master threads idle in an OpenMP barrier while the master thread manages the communication. Figure 12 shows the usage of the barriers in the slave threads of each MPI task for the `sbc_wave` subroutine. This strategy is used in all the parallel regions of the code.

Figure 12: Imbalance of two nodes running the `sbc_wave` subroutine (zoom applied). In red, we can see the time spent in computation, while in blue we see threads entering a synchronization barrier and waiting there until the last thread finishes his portion of computation

The next hotspot region that we analyzed is the `ice_dyn_rdgfft`, which represents the 20% of the whole NEMO timestep. In Figure 13 we see the useful duration (left) and the correlation of useful duration with instructions (right). Looking at these two plots we reach similar conclusions as in the previous region: we identify a load imbalance issue both among OpenMP threads and among MPI processes. Looking at the correlation of useful duration and number of instructions, we can conclude that the load imbalance is caused by some processes and threads executing more instructions than others, which is produced by a non-homogeneous distribution of work.

Figure 13: Useful duration zoom to some processes of the ice_dyn_dgrft subroutine (left) and number of instructions (colour) per process (y-axis) for the useful duration (x-axis) (right)

Looking at the source code of this ice_dyn_rdgft subroutine, we noticed that computation occurs only in those domain cells where ice is present, generating a strong imbalance across the domain. This imbalance propagates to subsequent subroutine calls.

Finally, we analysed the icedyn_rhg_evp and dynspg_ts subroutines which cover the 12% and 19% of the full NEMO timestep respectively. In Figure 14 we can see two different plots corresponding to the two subroutines. In the top traces, we see the MPI calls that are colour-coded as seen in the legend. In the bottom traces we see the useful duration of the computation, green means low values (short computation bursts), blue means high values, and grey represents non-useful time, i.e., the threads are not doing useful work, just waiting in an MPI call or inside the OpenMP runtime.

Figure 14: Zoom into some processes of the icedyn_rhg_evp(left) and dynspg_ts (right) subroutine for the MPI calls (top) and the useful duration (down)

The first observation is that these two regions present a very low granularity in computation. Looking at Figure 14 we observe that there are short bursts of computation followed by several MPI communication calls. The pattern in the MPI communication phase is always the same: two MPI_Isend, two MPI_Recv, two MPI_Isend, two MPI_Recv, and finally, four MPI_Wait. The time spent in MPI is the main bottleneck of these regions. The dynspg_ts subroutine has an even worse granularity of the computation burst.

This profiling shows different computational aspects that can be improved and we will try to optimise. First, regarding the OpenMP implementation we have detected some synchronisations that impact the performance and can be deleted while keeping the data dependencies. We have also found that the load balance in the OpenMP regions can be optimised using a different strategy. Finally, the MPI implementation can be improved using a better MPI placing.

1.3.3 I/O profiling analysis

1.3.3.1 Introduction

The IFS-NEMO model uses an output schema that incorporates I/O servers, which allow the data to be processed and stored in parallel with the model execution. Specifically, the IFS output is handled by the IFS-embedded servers, while the NEMO output is handled entirely by the MultIO library. This schema best suits achieving the maximum throughput in high-resolution simulation. Nevertheless, it still has potential for optimization and requires monitoring to ensure data handling does not compromise the model's efficiency.

To support I/O performance, we applied profiling to identify possible bottlenecks and opportunities for optimization and developed a methodology to ensure the best resource distribution between servers.

1.3.3.2 I/O servers' scalability and bottleneck identification

To make the most efficient use of the available resources, we developed a methodology to determine the optimal server configuration for any simulation, which will be described below.

We start from a pre-optimized I/O configuration that will ideally be selected using insights from previous experiments and the output plans, mainly focusing on how many grids and resolutions the data will be written. We run an experiment with this configuration simulating five days; upon completion, statistics from different functions are stored. For this step, we focus on the ones affected by the IFS servers: IOSERV: 'IOSERV - RECLAIM BUF SPACE' and IOSERV: 'IOSERV - SEND MDL'

- IOSERV: 'IOSERV - RECLAIM BUF SPACE': This function measures the time client processes wait for server buffers to empty before sending messages. If this function takes a significant amount of time, it indicates that the IFS servers lack sufficient resources, as the buffer data is not being processed quickly enough.

- IOSEV: 'IOSEV - SEND MDL': This function measures the time taken to send messages from the client side. It may indicate network congestion or insufficient bandwidth if it takes a considerable amount of time.

Both functions should report a percentage of total execution time inferior to one per cent to advance to the next step. Otherwise, the IFS servers will require an increment of resources, usually of 25%, until the condition is met.

Next, we focus on the NEMO servers. Insufficient resources here do not block the model but cause data accumulation, leading to out-of-memory errors or delayed output. We reduce the NEMO servers by half and check the overall execution duration. If it increases by more than 1%, we reverse the last adjustment and reduce the rate of resource reduction until we achieve an optimal balance or the resource allocation becomes too low for meaningful experimentation.

Finally, in the last step, we repeat the resource reduction for the IFS servers using the methodology of the previous step. Figure 15 represents the methodology in a graphical way.

Figure 15: Flux diagram showcasing the methodology to optimise resource distribution to I/O servers

Table 3 demonstrates the results obtained from a simulation using the target resolution Tco1279-eORCA12 executed on LUMI-G. Initially, more resources were used than necessary. By applying the methodology, we reduced the number of nodes by 18 while maintaining the same throughput, achieving a 6.67% increase in efficiency.

Tco1279-eORCA12 resolution LUMI-G (6.67% efficiency increase)					
	Compute nodes	IFS I/O nodes	NEMO I/O nodes	Total nodes	SDPD
Initial configuration	256	16	16	288	350
Final configuration	256	12	2	270	349

Table 3: Comparison between the initial server configuration and the final configuration obtained after executing the proposed methodology

1.3.3.3 MultIO action profiling

Our profiling study specifically targeted the MultIO library, this decision was based on several key considerations:

MultIO is a newly developed library still in progress, offering more substantial optimization opportunities compared to the more mature IFS post-processing and output schema. Additionally, although MultIO is currently part of the IFS output pipeline, acting as a client within the Fortran IFS server, there are plans for MultIO to replace it entirely. This would involve managing communication and server creation, as it already does with NEMO.

Initially, we instrumented broadly the different MultIO actions in order to understand the importance of these to the total time spent by I/O.

The results of the profiling are shown in Table 4; the actions are divided between being performed on the model side and, therefore, directly affecting the throughput or on the server side, which indirectly affects the throughput because depending on the efficiency of these actions, more resources are required to be allocated on the servers. The metadata mapping and statistics actions are the most time-consuming on the client side. In contrast, among server actions, the one highlighted is the interpolation, representing almost 90% of the time.

These results were obtained by encoding and writing the data in GRIB format; the final objective is to have the data outputted in NetCDF format. For this reason, the future implementation could vary the encode, sink and possibly other action timings.

MultIO action timings development configuration LUMI-C			
N_Fields=153	N_timesteps=12 (Between outputs)	N_Servers=32	All_Fields=1528
NEMO Model side			
	Avg burst-time	Avg number of burst per process	Avg time
Select	0.005 ms	All_Fields*N_timesteps_	5.9%
Metadata-mapping	0.044 ms	N_Fields*N_timesteps	52.2%
Statistics	0.034 ms	N_Fields*N_timesteps	40.4%
Transport	0.147 ms	N_Fields	1.45%
NEMO Server side			
	Avg burst-time	Avg number of burst per process	Avg time
Select	0.005ms	N_Fields*N_timesteps/N_servers	< 0.1%
Aggregate	0.010ms	N_Fields*N_timesteps/N_servers	< 0.1%
Mask	24.1 ms	N_Fields/N_servers	1.4%
Interpolate	1585 ms	N_Fields/N_servers	89.6%
Metadata-mapping	0.044 ms	N_Fields/N_servers	< 0.1%
Encode	101.45 ms	N_Fields/N_servers	5.7%
Sink	9.6 ms	N_Fields/N_servers	< 0.1%

Table 4: MultIO actions profiling on NEMO, showcasing the average burst time, the number of bursts with respect to the number of fields, servers and timesteps, and the average total time consumed by the action on the model and server side

1.3.3.4 MultiIO metadata mapping and statistics actions

The metadata mapping action contains a unique flow that creates and modifies the metadata associated with a message if it is a field. The average burst time is relatively small compared with other actions, such as transport. However, the fact that every field and every timestep generates a message that must be mapped increases the average time spent in this action.

The case of the statistics actions is more complex. It consists of four differentiated parts that are not necessarily executed with the same frequency.

- **The setup (1).** It generates a unique message key by reading and concatenating pieces of the previously set metadata. It is executed as many times as fields and steps there are.
- **Initialise temporal statistics (2).** Only done if they are not already created for this message.
- **End of temporal window (3).** It applies the computation iterating over statistical operations
- **Update of the temporal window (4).** It is performed after the computation has finished.

Statistics section	Average duration	Times executed
Statistics 1	0.034ms	TF * nemo total timesteps
Statistics 2	0.022ms	TF
Statistics 3	0.026ms	E
Statistics 4	0.010ms	E

Table 5: Timing of the different sections inside the statistics action
 TF -> Total number of fields outputted by the plans.

E -> Number of fields that are outputted inside the time window. Taking as an example a 1 year simulation the total value of E would be the amount of fields that are outputted monthly * 12 months + fields outputted daily * 365 days + fields outputted hourly * 365 days * 24 hours.

Table 5 contains the timings of the different sections of the statistics as well as the frequency of its execution. The section with higher average duration and more time executed is the setup or statistics 1, which accesses the metadata and generates a key from it. Currently, MultiIO developers are in progress of refactoring the way MultiIO handles the metadata, when it is finished a reevaluation will be done to see if it is still an expensive section.

1.3.3.5 MultiIO interpolation

While studying the MultiIO interpolation action to find possible optimisations, we noticed that OpenMP was disabled for some of the libraries MultiIO uses to execute the interpolation: MIR and ECKIT. The reason was a conflict between the pthreads created by MultiIO servers and the CCE OpenMP library, which does not admit threads outside the main one to enter a parallel region. We modified the code to solve the issue and profiled the model to assess the impact:

Figure 16 contains two Extrae views. The top view represents the interpolation action, where the green part corresponds to the MultiIO setup, which is negligible, and the red part represents the MIR job execution. The bottom view shows the OpenMP region on the same timeline, which, when compared, does not constitute a considerable percentage of the interpolation action.

Figure 16: Top plot corresponding to one MultiIO interpolation burst (red part corresponds to MIR and green part to MultiIO setup), bottom plot corresponding to OpenMP regions

Table 6 presents the time spent in the function called within the interpolation, with and without OpenMP support. The total time reflects the accumulated time of each process and thread. Therefore, the right column (with OpenMP) in the table shows a higher total time, while other metrics, such as averages, are smaller. The time spent by the server in this OpenMP function corresponds to the maximum time reported, which is 338 and 93 ms for w/o and w/ OpenMP respectively.

Total	2,658.53 ms	Total	3,797.75 ms
Average	332.32 ms	Average	79.12 ms
Maximum	338.62 ms	Maximum	93.84 ms
Minimum	326.68 ms	Minimum	61.47 ms
StDev	4.48 ms	StDev	8.99 ms
Avg/Max	0.98	Avg/Max	0.84

Table 6: Left: time spent in the function when OpenMP is disabled. Right: time spent in function when OpenMP is enabled and set to 6 threads. The timeline comprehends 1 daily output from NEMO with the Tco79-eORCA1 configuration

In this case, for the Tco79-eORCA1 resolution, there was an average reduction of 0.24 seconds in the interpolation action per output step, each corresponding to a simulated day. Which overall is not a significant improvement. In the future, we aim to test the changes with the development configuration, using Marenostrom 5, which has an environment more compatible with the BSC tools, allowing us to have more detailed OpenMP information.

1.3.4 IFS checks and diagnostics impact

During the first profiling of the IFS model, we discovered that the routines SPNORM and GPNORM, which are used for the normalisation of physical quantities to maintain the accuracy and stability of numerical computations and for other diagnostic purposes, can potentially impact the performance depending on the frequency they are called and the number of diagnostics enabled.

To check the impact of these checks, we executed the Tco1279-eORCA12 resolution changing the value of the NMRDIAGLEV parameter, which enables/disables GPNORM diagnostic checks; and the NFRSDI/NFRGDI parameters, which controls the frequency of the SPNORM and GPNORM checks respectively.

Table 7 shows the throughput results of disabling the non-required checks and changing the frequency of SPNORM/GPNORM compared with the baseline default values. Results are an average of three executions with 32 computing nodes for a 1-day forecast. The speedup achieved by disabling GPNORM checks is 4.5 % and changing the frequency of SPNORM/GPNORM is 4.2%, which potentially combined can achieve nearly a 10% speedup.

IFS checks impact	Default values	Disable GPNORM checks	Change SPNORM/GPNORM frequency
Parameters	NMRDIAGLEV=1 NFRSDI= 1 NFRGDI = 1	NMRDIAGLEV = 0 NFRSDI = 1 NFRGDI = 1	NMRDIAGLEV=1 NFRSDI = 192 NFRGDI = 192
Throughput (SDPD)	131.2	136.8	137.1

Table 7: Throughput comparison for the default configuration and disabling two types of IFS checks. Average of three executions Tco1279-eORCA12 with 32 nodes on LUMI-G

Another diagnostic studied in this context was the frequency of the DDH diagnostics, used by the scientists to ensure the correctness of the simulation. The parameter that controls this diagnostic is NFRDHP, so we followed the same approach to check the performance impact of this diagnostic. Table 8 shows the impact of DDH, for an average of three executions of Tco1279-eORCA12 with 32 computing nodes on LUMI-G. We can see that the speedup is 4.2%, similar to the results of Table 7.

IFS DDH impact	DDH every step	DDH every 192 steps
Parameters	NFRDHP = 1	NFRDHP = 192
Throughput (SDPD)	131.2	137.2

Table 8: Throughput comparison for the DDH diagnostics. Average of three executions Tco1279-eORCA12 with 32 nodes on LUMI-G

In these two cases shown in Tables 7 and 8, we can see that the frequency on each parameter has a small impact on the throughput of the model (~4%) but the combination of them can achieve a not negligible impact on the performance, around 10%. It is important to set these checks according to the scientific requirements and maximise the frequency of each of them.

1.3.5 LUMI environment variables

During the deployment of the first version of IFS-NEMO on LUMI-G, we aimed to avoid model crashes by configuring several MPI environment variables to ensure a stable run. However, the throughput achieved on LUMI-G fell below our expectations, prompting us to investigate these variables to understand their potential impact on performance.

1.3.5.1 LUMI-G

First, we analysed if all the variables introduced were strictly necessary; some were not and could be removed, improving the throughput. We then tested the different values and most possible combinations for the rest of the variables. We executed the test with Tco1279-eORCA12 resolution employing 256 compute nodes, 16 IFS I/O nodes and 16 MultiIO nodes and simulating a 1-day forecast. The conclusion reached for the different variables is shown in Table 9.

ENV Variable	Value	Are they indispensable for the model execution?
MPICH_OFI_NIC_POLICY	NUMA	No
MPICH_ASYNC_PROGRESS	1	Yes
MPICH_OFI_STARTUP_CONNECT	1	No
MPICH_MEMORY_REPORT	0	No
AMD_SERIALIZE_COPY	3	No
AMD_SERIALIZE_KERNEL	3	No
FI_CXI_OFLOW_BUF_COUNT	4	No
MPICH_GPU_SUPPORT_ENABLED	0	Yes
MPICH_GPU_SUPPORT_ENABLED	1	Yes
FI_CXI_OPTIMIZED_MRS	false	Yes
FI_CXI_RX_MATCH_MODE	hybrid	No
MPICH_SMP_SINGLE_COPY_MODE	NONE	No
MPICH_ALLTOALL_INTRA_ALGORITHM	pairwise	No
FI_CXI_EQ_ACK_BATCH_SIZE	1	No
FI_CXI_DEFAULT_CQ_SIZE	131072	No
FI_CXI_OFLOW_BUF_SIZE	268435456	No
FI_CXI_DEFAULT_TX_SIZE	32768	No

Table 9: List of environment variables tested and if they are necessary

1.3.5.2 LUMI-C

For LUMI-C the environment variables defined are `FI_CXI_RX_MATCH_MODE` and `MPICH_ABORT_ON_ERROR`. The latter is irrelevant to performance because it only affects the behaviour after encountering an error. Therefore, we focused on the possible combinations of `FI_CXI_RX_MATCH_MODE`, which controls how the message-matching process is handled using hardware, software or a hybrid approach. The results are displayed in Table 10, where there is a slight improvement in the hardware mode concerning the other two.

Parameters	FI_CXI_RX_MATCH_M ODE=Hybrid	FI_CXI_RX_MATCH_MO DE=Software	FI_CXI_RX_MATCH_M ODE=Hardware
CNT4 (s)	659.6	672.7	635.4
SDPD (throughput)	131.2	130.2	136.3

Table 10: Execution time and throughput comparison changing the value of FI_CXI_RX_MATCH_MODE used

1.3.6 NEMO mixed precision plan

Over the past decade, mixed precision techniques have gained popularity due to their potential to significantly enhance performance by optimising the precision of each variable in the code. However, manually implementing these techniques can be highly complex. To address this, the Barcelona Supercomputing Center developed a tool called AutoRPE, which automates this process for Fortran codes. AutoRPE is based on the RPE library, a reduced-precision emulator created at ECMWF by A. Dawson and P. Düben. Given an input Fortran 90 code and a specific run configuration, AutoRPE can identify the variables that must retain double precision to ensure accurate results.

In this project, we aim to use AutoRPE to create a mixed-precision version of NEMO to be coupled with IFS, which already runs in single precision. While newer releases of NEMO (V4.2) include a mixed-precision version, the version chosen for the EERIE project (V4.0) required us to start from scratch. Our first challenge was integrating the ifs-bundle into our workflow. The original tool operates fully automatically, including downloading sources from official repositories (e.g., GitLab, Bitbucket, SVN) and data from the cloud (e.g., NEMO input datasets on Zenodo). However, we had to deviate from this intended behaviour since our code is a modified version of NEMO from the NextGems configuration, and our input data came from spin-up runs not stored on any cloud repository. We adapted those parts of the workflow accordingly and modified some ifs-bundle CMake rules to produce the intermediate pre-processed files for NEMO required by AutoRPE. This task was more challenging than anticipated due to the complexity of the compilation process, the lengthy compiling time (around two hours), and frequent failures when the compilation was not started from scratch.

Without delving into the implementation details, it is important to note that the emulator needs to parse the preprocessed files. Once these files were produced, we had to develop additional features for AutoRPE to handle specific coding patterns not previously encountered by the emulator. Initially, the MultIO implementation was not ready, so we used XIOS, NEMO's default I/O server, and spent time tuning the XML files for XIOS, as the spin-ups were run with native NEMO output.

With everything ready, we began a preliminary analysis with 1896 variables using an eORCA1 configuration on Marenostrom4, the former Barcelona Supercomputing Center's HPC. This analysis involved 847 simulations, identifying 431 variables (~23% of the total) that needed to remain in double precision. We then implemented these changes in the actual code to run a

simulation without the emulator and verify the results. Additional tests to further improve the analysis will be performed in the new Marenostrum5 machine.

Adapting NEMO to use mixed precision has the potential to yield significant performance gains. Reducing the precision of a substantial proportion of variables not only decreases memory usage but also enhances computational efficiency through improved vectorization and more operations per instruction. While theoretically, switching from double to single precision could double the performance, the actual gains depend on various factors. These include the number of variables that can use reduced precision, the computational resources employed, and the coupling of the ocean model with other components of the Earth System Model (ESM). In scenarios where MPI communication becomes the primary performance bottleneck—especially when using a large number of resources—the impact of mixed precision may be less pronounced. Based on our preliminary tests with the eORCA1 configuration, we anticipate performance improvements in the range of 20–30% for the ocean component. These gains are significant and justify the effort invested in adapting the code.

Once the full variable set analysis is complete, we will update the precision of variables in the original code and make additional modifications to ensure compatibility. We will then validate the mixed-precision version against reference simulations (double precision experiments) to ensure minimal deviation. Initially, this will be done using an eORCA1 grid, but our ultimate goal is a version compatible with the eORCA12 configuration. For the eORCA12 grid, we will not repeat the analysis due to the extensive simulation time required. Instead, we will apply the precision settings derived from the eORCA1 analysis and validate this configuration against observational data, avoiding the computational expense of reference runs for eORCA12.

1.3.7 NEMO GPU transition plan

1.3.7.1 The code transition strategy

The approach of transitioning a large-scale existing program code to accelerators typically imposes step-by-step actions. The NEMO program code, as it often happens, was not designed to be offloaded to accelerators, so code adaptation is required from the perspective of the memory heterogeneous nature of hybrid CPU multicore + GPU accelerator systems. To start with, we enumerate some code regions that can be transitioned to accelerators using directive-based OpenMP or OpenACC parallel programming models [1, 2].

Due to the memory heterogeneity of the system, we either use vendor-dependent methods for Unified Memory [3] allocations or use explicit or implicit data transfer directives of the directive-based parallel programming model. In the latter case, data transfers are done before and after running the accelerator kernel to ensure workflow consistency. As it is known that the data copies to and from accelerator memory are slow due to both high latency and limited bandwidth of such operations, the resulting full workflow can be slow enough even though the separate kernels are accelerated. This is a known issue for this porting phase. At this stage we do not try to get a

running time boost for the whole process, we only try to set up the baseline for the code transition process. We choose the methodologies and technologies applicable to a target HPC system, and we understand the set of OpenMP or OpenACC directives for typical loops in a source code that lead to a good level of code acceleration. In the following transition steps, we try to port more source code loops using the same approach, choosing first the loops that follow each other in the workflow so that accelerator data copies could be avoided. When the continuous region of several loops is transitioned to the accelerator, we can estimate the performance benefits for the first time. The analysis should help to plan further steps of the code transition.

From the software engineering point of view, it is important to carefully check the code correctness after each step and sub-step of the transition process. The checks must be done using automated methods and facilitate the most up-to-date software engineering techniques. The research on which programming models and memory models must be used is also a mandatory step. The choice between OpenMP, OpenACC, and possibly other models, as well as the decision on the Unified Memory approach using, must be done as a result of analysis of a target HPC system hardware and system software traits.

That means that the transition strategy should include three basic steps, followed by further planning based on the results achieved. These are:

- Preliminary steps: constructing a reliable development and testing environment; hardware and system software traits analysis, resulting in the programming model and memory model choice.
- The transition of several significantly time-consuming loops as a proof of concept. This step can be combined with wider research on the tools, libraries and technologies that can facilitate the transition process. Because of the limited time planned for the transition process, we prefer to have an option to vary the actual timeline and the volume of this research.
- The transition of a large enough continuous workflow region eliminating redundant data transfers
- Transition results analysis and further planning

1.3.7.2 Preliminary steps

As for the software engineering point of view, the work on constructing the development and testing environment is going on. The environment on the LUMI-G partition of the LUMI supercomputer is set up, including:

- The build scripts are tuned for the set of compilers and libraries that are in use on the partition
- NEMO test case based on eORCA1 grid
- Testing script doing the sanity check of the built binary:
 - By comparing reported reduction results for global model fields such as velocity components

- By checking internal timers related to target source code functions
- Simplest possible standalone NEMO tests with smallest available grids on the first (quickest) testing stage and integration tests for the IFS bundle for more comprehensive testing. The standalone tests are designed to be run fully automated; IFS bundle tests are supposed to be run manually by the workflow team using a pull request review approach.

After studying the target HPC system characteristic of the LUMI supercomputer, and specifically the LUMI-G partition features, these conclusions were made:

- Both the OpenACC parallel programming model and OpenMP parallel programming model can be used. It is reasonable to start the transition process on the basis of the OpenMP model as this model is defined by a more vendor-independent specification. Nevertheless, we consider switching to OpenACC during the first attempts of the transition process if we face significant issues with the OpenMP implementation on a target platform
- Direct GPU transfers can be used as this functionality is provided by hardware and MPI library, the real bandwidth of exchanges has been measured
- The CPU and accelerator code workflows can be efficiently combined, since the optimal running modes for both models seem to match. The observed 8-threads per MPI process optimal configuration is probably very close to the LUMI-G specific 7-thread per MPI process configuration (with 8 MPI ranks per node). At the same time, for GPU code, 8 MPI ranks per node configuration allows to directly use 8 accelerator cards per node with 1:1 rank-to-card ratio. That means that optimal modes for both CPU and GPU instruction flow can be reached within a single configuration.
- The pinned memory has a significant benefit in host-to-device and device-to-host transfer rates. It means that we have to develop the strategy of optimal usage of pinned memory as a part of transition process
- (Work In Progress) The support of Unified Memory and optimal ways to utilise this memory model still requires consideration.

1.3.7.3 Transition of several significantly time-consuming loops

The choice of loops for the first transition steps is made according to the basic criteria: by profiling, we try to find the loops or groups of loops in the source code that take a significant portion of the running time and are mostly compute-intensive. We then classify these loops into four basic groups: - Those covered by existing OpenMP regions and looking as if they can be switched to OpenMP target offload or OpenACC in a straight-forward way. - Those covered by existing OpenMP regions, but have 'omp barrier', 'omp master' directives inside, and/or many MPI exchange sections inside the 'omp master' - Those not covered by OpenMP regions, but looking as if there are no obstacles of transition them both to OpenMP and OpenACC - Those not covered by OpenMP and have questionable prospects of the transition.

Tables 11, 12, 13 and 14 summarise these source code regions.

Subroutine	Source code	Internal timer	Comment
<i>adv_x</i>	<i>icedyn_adv_pra.F90:439-600</i>	<i>ice_dyn_adv_pra_adv_x</i>	Single OpenMP region
<i>adv_y</i>	<i>icedyn_adv_pra.F90:645-813</i>	<i>ice_dyn_adv_pra_adv_y</i>	Single OpenMP region
<i>zdf_evd</i>	<i>zdfevd.F90:75-132</i>	<i>zdf_edv</i>	The subroutine contains the OpenMP region and 2 more calls at the end: 1) call iom_put ; 2) call trd_tra . Timer covers the whole subroutine
<i>tra_zdf_imp</i>	trazdf.F90:78-93 (trazdf.F90:120-287)	<i>tra_zdf_imp</i>	Single OpenMP region

Table 11: OpenMP regions that can be transited to OpenACC

Subroutine	Source code	Internal timer	Comment
<i>tra_ldf_iso</i>	<i>traldf_iso.F90:135-419</i>	<i>tra_ldf_iso</i>	Single OpenMP region, but it has omp barriers inside the “tracer loop”, and a serialized region that makes call dia_ptr_hst add the end of each tracer loop iteration
<i>sbc_stokes</i>	<i>sbcwave.F90:133-304</i>	<i>sbc_stokes</i>	Single OpenMP region, but it has omp barrier inside, 2 sections MPI calls in omp master
???	<i>domvvl.F90:???</i>	???	Analysis In Progress
???	<i>dynzdf.F90:???</i>	???	Analysis In Progress

Table 12: OpenMP with barriers and serial parts

Subroutine	Source code	Internal timer	Comment
<i>dyn_ldf_lap</i>	<i>dynldf_lap_blp.F90:133-138</i>	no specific timer, part of <i>dyn_ldf</i>	Some basic calculation loops inside
<i>bbl</i> , <i>tra_bbl_diff</i> , <i>tra_bbl_adv</i>	<i>trabbl.F90:116-152</i>	<i>tra_bbl</i> combines these subroutines and other subroutines	Some calculations loop inside

Table 13: Regions that are non-OpenMP yet

Subroutine	Source code	Internal timer	Comment
<i>dia_wri</i>	<i>diawri.F90:0-420</i>	<i>dia_wri</i>	Creates standard output files, many calls to subroutines <i>histbeg</i> , <i>histvert</i> , <i>histdef</i> , <i>wheneq</i> . The transition prospects are questionable

Table 14: Regions that are non-OpenMP and hardly can be transited

The research process that can be continued in parallel with the first kernels transition process, and that can contribute to it should include at least the directions: - To look at the results of previous or ongoing efforts of NEMO code transition: can we learn from the ideas they use and the results they achieve? At least, the current results of applying the PSyclone tool to NEMO 4.0 and 4.2 codes (<https://psyclone.readthedocs.io/en/stable/nemo.html>) - To find the libraries that can work as building blocks for constructing the transformed code. At least, we can explore the option of using the library FILED API, that is actively used in the DEODE project, to facilitate host-device data transfers - To find the tools that help to analyse NEMO subroutines in order to get more information on their structure and help in the transition process. At least, the REVEAL tool by Cray, Loki and PSyclone tools might be applied for code regions analysis and transformations. - To investigate the spectrum of profiling tools and methods to be fully equipped to quickly learn performance differences in the transformed blocks. At least a variety of AMD and Cray tools: rocprof, Omnitrace, CrayPat, Apprentice2 are worth investigating. The research process is planned to overlap with the first attempts of real code transitions to implement a more flexible schedule, where some processes can be reordered or omitted to match the tight time constraints of the whole transition process.

2 Impact and exploitation

There is one objective of the project connected to Task M2.1 and this deliverable:

O3: Reduce by at least 50 % the time and energy needed to produce climate information with the highest level of process fidelity.

Although the objective is not fully achieved yet, we are currently going into this direction as shown by the different continuing computational developments described in this document. In addition, BSC has started contacting some partners in the project to provide its HPC expertise in order to assess the computational efficiency of the different models used for the EERIE simulations by conducting a profiling analysis, as well as suggesting improvements for potential bottlenecks.

3 General issues and workarounds

There have been several issues which required finding different workarounds:

- **Queue time and limited usage.** Since LUMI was the only powerful platform available (MN5 suffered an important delay), it caused us to compete for resources; we had to wait days or even weeks to test the changes done with the development configuration. Also, we were blocked if LUMI had any issues or ongoing maintenance.
- **Out of memory errors.** We encountered out-of-memory issues with high-resolution simulations.
- **OpenMP not traceable on LUMI using Extrae.** The BSC tracing tool Extrae is not yet compatible with Cray OpenMP, which prevents us from accessing OpenMP information. As a workaround, we utilised an OpenMP tracer library that enabled Extrae to record basic information, such as at the start and end of parallel regions.
- **PAPI counters unavailability on LUMI at the start of 2023.** PAPI counters were not available on LUMI. So, we had to do profiling on Marenostrum 4, and repeat the same on LUMI later.
- **MultIO NEMO transport, message hanging.** After enabling the complete output plans, we encountered hangs while running high-resolution experiments. As a workaround, we had to enable the `MPICH_ASYNC_PROGRESS` environmental variable, which degraded the performance until we could identify and solve the issue.

4 Conclusions and future work

Some initial steps have been performed to make the coupled ICON model work on a heterogeneous setup using GPUs for the atmospheric component and CPUs for the oceanic component. However, there are plans to improve the throughput to achieve a more performant setup.

Regarding kilometer-scale IFS-FESOM simulations on the Jewels cluster, although some important computational improvements have been achieved, AWI will continue its efforts to increase the throughput. We plan to run our simulations on the GPU nodes of the Jewels cluster to assess

further performance improvements. Our focus will also remain on enhancing I/O performance and optimising ocean-atmosphere coupling efficiency.

Multiple efforts have been carried out and are still ongoing to improve the throughput of IFS-NEMO, including a scalability analysis on LUMI and Marenostrum 5, a detailed CPU and I/O performance analysis and some improvements regarding IFS scientific checks as well as LUMI environment variables. In particular, the profiling analysis has identified different important bottlenecks that will be addressed as future work, including a better OpenMP parallelization, to improve some specific MPI communication pattern, and an efficient I/O setup for MultIO. In addition, there are two promising ongoing optimizations that will improve the throughput: implement a mixed precision version of the NEMO eORCA12 configuration; and port computationally expensive regions of NEMO to GPUs.

Last but not least, in the context of the WP10 BSC will provide HPC expertise to the rest of partners to analyse their respective models in order to detect potential bottlenecks and suggest computational optimisations. This would also allow us to find common points across different models regarding optimizations in order to be more productive.

5 References

- [1] OpenMP specification. URL: <https://www.openmp.org/wp-content/uploads/OpenMP-API-Specification-5-2.pdf>
- [2] OpenCC specification. URL: <https://www.openacc.org/sites/default/files/inline-images/Specification/OpenACC-3.2-final.pdf>
- [3] Z. Jin and J. S. Vetter, "Evaluating Unified Memory Performance in HIP," 2022 IEEE International Parallel and Distributed Processing Symposium Workshops (IPDPSW), Lyon, France, 2022, pp. 562-568, doi: 10.1109/IPDPSW55747.2022.00096. (<https://www.osti.gov/servlets/purl/1883900>)
- [4] Barcelona Supercomputing Center. 2023. Extrae. <https://tools.bsc.es/extrae>
- [5] Barcelona Supercomputing Center. 2023. Paraver. <https://tools.bsc.es/paraver>
- [6] Marc Casas, Rosa Badia, and Jesús Labarta. 2008. Automatic analysis of speedup of MPI applications. In Proceedings of the 22nd annual international conference on Supercomputing (ICS '08). Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 349–358. <https://doi.org/10.1145/1375527.1375578>

